

MURRAY K DAHM

Date of Birth: 26 January 1972

EDUCATION:

- 1998 Master of Literature (Auckland); Thesis: *The Career and Writings of Sextus Julius Frontinus*.
1995 Master of Arts (Hons) in Ancient History (Auckland); Thesis: *The Genre of Military Tactical Literature and the Strategemata of Polyaeus of Macedon*.
1993 Bachelor of Arts (Auckland)

PUBLICATIONS; PEER REVIEWED ARTICLES:

- 2016 (*forthcoming*) 'In the Shieldwall with Waldere – a new context for Hildegyð's speech, ll. 12-22?' *The Heroic Age: A Journal of Early Medieval Northwestern Europe* 17. Online at <http://www.heroicage.org/issues/17/dahm.php>
2011 'Roman Frontier Signalling and the Order of the *fupark*' *The Journal of Indo-European Studies* 39 (Washington), pp. 1-12.
2009 'Performing Nero' *Didaskalia* 7.2 (London).
Online at <http://www.didaskalia.net/issues/vol7no2/dahm.html>
2008 'Not Twins at All: The Agora Oinochoe Reinterpreted' *Hesperia* 76.4 (Princeton), pp. 717-730.
2004 'Campgate Bronzes and Roman Fire Signalling' *CLASSICVM* 30.1 (Sydney) pp. 17-25.
2002 'Polyaeus of Macedon and Alexander the Great' *APXAIIOΓNΩΣΙΑ* 11, (Athens) pp. 29-46.
2001 'A Cursive P-Rune? Re-examining Latin Cursive Elements in *fupark* Development' *Amsterdamer Beiträge zur älteren Germanistik* 55 (Amsterdam), pp. 15-20.
1999 'A Hendiadys in the *Breviarium* of Festus: A Literary Festus?' *Prudentia* 31.1, (Auckland) pp. 15-22.
1996 'The Anomaly of Marius in Roman Republican Hero-Worship' *Stele* 1, (Armidale) pp. 61-69.

PUBLICATIONS; BOOKS:

- 2016 (*forthcoming*) *Breaking the Spartans; Epaminondas and Pelopidas* (Pen & Sword Military, Barnsley, South Yorkshire).

PUBLICATIONS; BOOK CHAPTERS:

- 2012 'Italy: Setting the Standard', *Great, Grand & Famous Opera Houses* (Arbon publishing, Sydney) pp. 20-65.
2012 'France: Pinnacles of Style', *Great, Grand & Famous Opera Houses* (Arbon publishing, Sydney) pp. 66-97.

PUBLICATIONS; GENERAL ARTICLES:

- 2017 'Hollywood's favourite Viking: Ragnar Lodbrok' *Medieval Warfare* 7.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 54-55.
- 2017 'Putting the pieces in place – Vespasian's far reaching (re)organisation of the empire' *Ancient Warfare* 10.6 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 37-41.
- 2016 'Silent, Unwashed and Downtrodden: Peasants on film' *Medieval Warfare* 6.6 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 54-55.
- 2016 'Through Modern Eyes. Engels on the German Peasants' War' *Medieval Warfare* 6.6 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 40-44.
- 2016 "'My men have turned to women!' Artemisia of Halicarnassus' *Ancient Warfare* 10.5 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 17-19.
- 2016 'A Modern Film in Medieval Garb: Kingdom of Heaven' *Medieval Warfare* 6.5 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 54-55.
- 2016 "'Wild People" Gerald of Wales on the 'conquest of Ireland' *Medieval Warfare* 6.4 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 9-12.
- 2016 'Hidden Cinema. Medieval Normans and Irish on film' *Medieval Warfare* 6.4 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 53-55.
- 2016 'Competing for the gods – The Four Crown Games' in *Ancient History* 5 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 14-19.
- 2016 'Learning from the Enemy. The *Strategikon* and the Sassanids' in *Medieval Warfare* 6.3 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 10-13.
- 2016 'King Arthur II. Medieval warfare in film' in *Medieval Warfare* 6.3 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 53-55.
- 2016 'King Arthur. Medieval warfare in film' in *Medieval Warfare* 6.2 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 49-50.
- 2016 'Talking the talk and walking the walk. Socrates at War' in *Ancient Warfare* 10.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 23-27.
- 2016 "'Deeds done beyond the Sea' – the *Historia* of William of Tyre' in *Medieval Warfare* 6.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 9-12.
- 2016 'The *Constitutio Antoniniana* – grant, grab, process, or something else?' in *Ancient History* 2 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 20-23.
- 2015 'Learning from the Romans – The use of Vegetius in the Middle Ages' in *Medieval Warfare* 5.6, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 50-53.
- 2015 'The Circumnavigation of Africa and more. Hanno's *Periplus*' in *Ancient History* 1, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 37-44.
- 2015 'The best of men – The court poets of Adb al-Rahman' in *Medieval Warfare* 5.4, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 10-13.
- 2015 'Wading through the quagmire of sources. The blame game' in *1415: the battle of Agincourt: Medieval Warfare Special 2015*, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 63-67.
- 2015 'The Shield-wall of Waldere. New evidence for Anglo-Saxon tactics' in *Medieval Warfare* 5.1, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 49-52.
- 2014 'Plucked from the notes of song. Blind Harry and the sources for William Wallace.' in *Medieval Warfare* 4.3, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 11-15.
- 2014 'Fallout from the East: Bad tidings for Christianity' in *1453: The Conquest of Constantinople: Medieval Warfare Special 2014*, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 48-52.
- 2014 'What did 'right-carrying' legionaries carry? Literal *Dexiolaboi*' in *Ancient Warfare* 8.1, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 43-47.

- 2014 ‘The *Second Pskovian Chronicle* - Prince among princes’ in *Medieval Warfare* 3.6, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 11-15.
- 2014 ‘In a brother’s shadow. The Parthian war of Lucius Verus’ in *Ancient Warfare* 7.6, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 17-21.
- 2013 ‘Waxing lyrical on the ideal warrior. Warfare and Greek Poetry’ in *Ancient Warfare* 7.4 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 43-47.
- 2013 ‘Watching History Happen. Medieval Warfare on Film’ *Medieval Warfare* at <http://www.karwansaraypublishers.com/cms/karwansaray/medieval-warfare/about-mw/readmore-mw/20-medieval-warfare/medieval-warfare-articles/200-watching-history-happen.html>
- 2012 ‘The *Taktika* of Nikephorus Ouranos – The Last in a long line’ in *Medieval Warfare* 2.6, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 14-17.
- 2012 ‘The important and intriguing sixteenth century Codex Wallerstein’ in *Medieval Warfare* 2.3, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 50-52.
- 2012 ‘Twins, Chariot Warfare and Late Geometric Art. Tricked!’ in *Ancient Warfare* 6.1, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 38-39.
- 2012 ‘Chainmail’s Terror Song – warfare in Anglo-Saxon Poetry’ in *Medieval Warfare* 2.1, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 10-12.
- 2011 ‘Opening the Lid. A decorated ivory box from Ephesus’ in *Ancient Warfare* 5.6, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 40-41.
- 2011 ‘Learning from the Master: The *Fechtbücher* of Hans Talhoffer’ in *Medieval Warfare* 1.4, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 49-52.
- 2011 ‘Don’t lose your head – head wounds, healing and helmets’ in *Ancient Warfare* 5.5, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 38-39.
- 2011 ‘The Toledo Roman helmet. The ring of truth’ in *Ancient Warfare* 5.4, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 38-39.
- 2011 ‘The Other Side. Arab Sources of the Conquest of al-Andalus’ in *Medieval Warfare* 1.3, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 3-5.
- 2011 ‘Warfare and Chivalry in the Hundred Years War. The Chronicles of Jean Froissart’ in *Medieval Warfare* 1.2, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 3-5.
- 2011 ‘Tank, terror weapon or battle taxi? The role of the chariot on the battlefield’ in *Ancient Warfare* 5.1, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 47-52.
- 2010 ‘“The shove” or not “the shove.” The *Othismos* question’ in *Ancient Warfare* 4.2 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 48-53.
- 2009 ‘An Ancient Enigma – Solving the secrets of ancient military signalling’ in *Ancient Warfare* 3.6, (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 50-53.
- 2009 ‘The arrow versus the spear. The *Breviarium* of Festus as a military handbook.’ in *Ancient Warfare* 3.5 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 48-51.
- 2009 ‘The Strategikon of Maurice’ in *Ancient Warfare* 3.4 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 50-53.
- 2009 ‘Machines of War. Athenaeus Mechanicus’ On Machines’ in *Ancient Warfare* 3.3 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp.50-53.
- 2009 ‘Vegetius’s Teachings. Learning from Vegetius’ *Epitoma Rei Militaris*’ in *Ancient Warfare* 3.2 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 48-51.
- 2009 ‘Vegetius’ Scholarship. The *Epitoma Rei Militaris* and its Sources’ in *Ancient Warfare* 3.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 48-51.
- 2008 ‘Paddlewheels and Scythed Chariots. The Anonymous’ *De Rebus Bellicis*’ in *Ancient Warfare* 2.6 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 46-50.

- 2008 'By Word of Mouth' in *Ancient Warfare* 2.5 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 48-51.
- 2008 'Command by Example Part 2: Polyaeus of Macedon' in *Ancient Warfare* 2.4 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 40-44.
- 2008 'Command by Example Part 1: Sextus Julius Frontinus' in *Ancient Warfare* 2.3 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 40-44.
- 2008 'Onasander's General' *Ancient Warfare* 2.2 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 40-43.
- 2008 'Read Your Homer' in *Ancient Warfare* 2.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 41-45.
- 2007 'Xenophon's Cavalry Commander' in *Ancient Warfare* 1.4 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 38-42.
- 2007 'Survive a Siege' in *Ancient Warfare* 1.3 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 40-44.
- 2007 'Make Camp!' in *Ancient Warfare* 1.2 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 41-45.
- 2007 'Teach yourself how to be a General' in *Ancient Warfare* 1.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp. 30-31.
- 2007 'The Next Alexander' in *Ancient Warfare* 1.1 (Rotterdam, Netherlands), pp.32-37.
- 2000 'Wargaming the Anglo-Saxons II: Ealdorman Byrhtnoth. The Battle of Maldon' in *Miniature Wargames* 206 July (Bournemouth, UK) pp. 7-10.
- 2000 'Wargaming the Anglo-Saxons I: Alfred the Great. The Battle of Ethandune' in *Miniature Wargames* 205 June (Bournemouth, UK) pp. 7-10.

PUBLICATIONS; REVIEW ARTICLES:

- 2014 Review of *A Gentleman's Guide to Duelling: Vincenzo Saviolo's Of Honour and Honourable Quarrels*, Edited and Presented by Jared Kirby (Frontline Books, Barnsley, 2013), *Ancient Warfare* 8.5 (Rotterdam), pp. .
- 2000 Review of Patricia Jeskins *The Environment and the Classical World*, Bristol Classical Press/Duckworth, 1998, *Prudentia* 32.2, (Auckland) pp. 196-199.
- 1999 Review of Jan Novák *Schola Cantans*, Bolchazy-Carducci, 1998, *Prudentia* 31.2, (Auckland) pp. 158-159.